

**AWARENESS, KNOWLEDGE, AND USES OF BROADCAST MEDIA
MESSAGES AGAINST DRUG ABUSE AMONG YOUTHS IN AWKA-SOUTH
LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA**

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Abstract

The dangers of drug abuse among youths have been a cause for concern in different societies of the world, prompting various stakeholders to seek means of preventing the malaise. Despite concerted efforts to create awareness of the dangers of drug abuse through diverse communication channels, the incidents reportedly seem to be on the rise, with the attendant negative impacts mostly on the youth. This paper examined how broadcast media messages have influenced the awareness, knowledge, and use of drugs among youths of Awka-South Local Government Area, Anambra State, Nigeria. The study was anchored on Social Learning and Cognitive Dissonance Theories; whereas, the survey research method was deployed with the questionnaire used as the tool for data collection. The results indicated, among others, that exposure to certain

types of media content, such as glamorized portrayals of drug use in television dramas, is associated with increased risk of drug abuse among youths. Consequently, the researchers recommend the use of educational campaigns to raise awareness on the harmful effects of drug abuse and counter the glamorization of illicit drug use in television dramas. Also, the use of a multimedia approach, including social media, was recommended as veritable means to reach the youth.

Keywords: Awareness, Broadcast Media, Drug Abuse, Knowledge, Messages, Public Health

Introduction

Drug abuse among youths has become a prevalent issue that poses significant socio-economic and health challenges in various societies globally. Lynch (2022) describes a drug as any chemical or biological substance that affects the function of the body. Drug or substance abuse is defined as the harmful use of psychoactive substances, including alcohol and illicit drugs, which are harmful to both users and society at large (WHO, 2019; Sloboda, 2020). It is an excessive, unauthorized, and addictive use of drugs for non-medical reasons. Studies have shown that the onset of drug consumption and its subsequent abuse begins in adolescent age (Nahvizadeh, Akhara, Arti, Qaraat, Geramian, Farjzadegan, & Heidari, 2014; Mazhari, Ziaddini, Nakhaee, & Kermanian, 2021).

Drug abuse and drug-related disorders have consistently plagued human society, and it has become an emerging global public health issue. The global estimate of drug users in 2021 was over 296 million people, which is seen as an increase of 23% over the previous decade (UNODC, 2023). According to the same report from UNODC in Nigeria, 14.4% of the Nigerian population between the ages of 15 and 64 abuse drugs. Similarly, UNODC (2023) reports that while the number of persons suffering from drug-related disorders has increased to 39.5 million in the last decade, the youth population is the most vulnerable and the most severely affected by drug or substance use disorder in many regions of the world. Africa is reportedly accounting for 70% of people in treatment who are below 35 years of age.

The prevalence of drug abuse, especially among the youths and the attendant negative consequences have been a course of concern for critical stakeholders in drug-related issues in Nigeria, such as the National Drug Law Enforcement Agency, (NDLEA), National Agency for Foods and Drugs Administration and Control, (NAFDAC), Pharmacists Council of Nigeria, (PCN), and the Presidential Advisory Committee on Drugs, (PACD), among others. These agencies and institutions are required to address this issue in many ways, including the use of broadcast media messages specifically tailored to the Nigerian context. Drugs

commonly abused by the youthful population include social drugs, such as cigarettes and alcohol; psychoactive drugs such as tramadol, amphetamines, methamphetamine, codeine, heroin, cannabis, and cocaine. According to the NDLEA Ogun State Commander, Ibiba Odili, during the launch of War Against Drug Abuse (WADA) in Abeokuta, "14.3m Nigerians involved in drug abuse are within the age of 15 and 64 years" (*Vanguard*, 2023)

This, perhaps, explains why concerted efforts have been in place to create awareness about the dangers of drug abuse or illicit substance abuse, especially among the younger generation. The broadcast media, including radio and television, are veritable tools in reaching targeted youths with messages created in diverse formats to educate them on the dangers inherent in drug abuse and how they can be adversely affected if they fail to desist from the negative act. Changing socio-cultural dynamics and increased exposure to various substances have contributed to the increasing incidence of drug abuse among the young population.

Consequently, it is believed that the incidences of drug abuse could be curbed using various broadcast media messages such as news, features, documentaries, sit-coms, family shows, reality shows, discussion, talks, commercials, public service announcements, magazine programmes, and so on in creating awareness and disseminating essential content that can increase the knowledge regarding the risks associated with the problem among the youths. This is because the capacity of the broadcast media to reach millions of the audience, widely, in a diverse, scattered location, simultaneously, has been utilized by diverse groups, institutions, and agencies across the globe. In health, education, science, and engineering, for instance, the media of communication, especially the broadcast media, have played significant roles in behaviour change communication and in the transformation of society (Anwar, Malik, Raees & Anwar, 2020; Saei, Valadi, Karimi & Khammarmia, 2021; Elom, Uwakwe, Akpa & Uwaleke, 2025).

Hence, disseminating anti-drug abuse messages through the broadcast media is perceived as one of the ways to curb drug abuse to its barest minimum. The broadcast media are potent tools against drug abuse (Nwokedi, Akata & Okafor, 2023). Effective prevention and control strategies require raising awareness, enhancing knowledge, and utilizing mass media campaigns to disseminate messages against drug abuse. Apart from their wide reach, the broadcast media platforms are flexible in language use, and can penetrate hard-to-reach areas, making them suitable for targeting large audiences, including youths, and delivering consistent and persuasive messages for behaviour change. How the

youths respond to these messages becomes a subject of investigation to guide policy-makers in their pattern of policy formation for drug use and control.

This study explored the level of awareness, knowledge, and use of broadcast media messages against drug abuse among youths residing in Awka-South Local Government Area (LGA) of Anambra State, Nigeria. It was primarily targeted to derive valuable insights for designing and implementing effective intervention programmes on drug abuse prevention among young people.

More than 2.6 million people aged 10-24 die annually from drug and substance abuse (WHO, 2019). The increasing prevalence of drug abuse and drug-related deaths in many societies of the world, including Nigeria, despite awareness of its risks, calls for effective preventive measures. The worrisome nature of the effects of illicit substance abuse for all ages and the potential risk to the youth population, have made the need to seek ways to sensitize the most vulnerable population about the ugly trend by all possible means, including through information sharing and awareness of the inherent dangers of drug and substance abuse.

Broadcast media are considered powerful tools for disseminating information to influence behaviour change. Regardless of concerted efforts by critical stakeholders, such as the Nigerian Drug Law Enforcement Agency, NDLEA, and other agencies of the Federal Government of Nigeria to end drug abuse with the attendant negative consequences, the youths' involvement in it seems unabated in the country. It becomes expedient to investigate to what extent the targeted youths have been positively influenced by the broadcast media messages, by ascertaining whether they are aware, whether they actually know, and whether they put the messages to effective use. This has become necessary as the researchers have not seen available studies that have provided solutions to the subject of this study. Thus, this paper firstly assessed the youths in Awka-South LGA's level of awareness about drug abuse and its risks. Secondly, it examined the youths' knowledge of broadcast media messages about drug abuse in the area. Thirdly, the paper investigated the extent to which youths in the area use broadcast media messages in making decisions about drug use. Fourthly, it identified the factors influencing the effectiveness of broadcast media messages in preventing drug abuse among youths in the area.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Broadcast Media and the Fight Against Drug Abuse

The issue of drug abuse among the youth is a growing concern in today's technology-driven society. Drug abuse is the use of illegal drugs or the use of

prescriptions or over-the-counter drugs for purposes other than those for which they are meant to be used, or in excessive amounts (National Cancer Institute (NCI), n.d.). The use of broadcast media as a tool for disseminating messages against the drug abuse menace among youths has been widely recognized by stakeholders, in addition to community engagements. Perhaps that is why NAFDAC runs a grassroots campaign tagged 'Youth Against Drug Abuse' (YAGA), through broadcast media outfits in Nigeria. According to Adeyeye (2018), apart from NAFDAC's routine inspections, seizures, and destruction of unwholesome drugs in the markets and elsewhere, the need to create awareness about this problem and provide accurate knowledge to help combat the spread of drug abuse among the younger generation is crucial. Similarly, the NDLEA's War Against Drug Abuse (WADA, launched in June 2021, during President Muhammadu Buhari's regime, to promote anti-drug culture through the broadcast media, is another good example.

However, one effective method of spreading awareness and knowledge about anti-drug culture is through broadcast media messages. The messages disseminated through various channels such the television, radio, and film have the potential to reach a wide audience and influence their behaviour positively. However, to achieve the desired goal, it has been observed that "the way and how the mass media were deployed would help them towards the realisation of a particular society" (Edogor, Ambassador-Brikins & Ezika, 2020, p.21). Radio in particular is quite ubiquitous, and it has played significant roles in mass mobilization, education, and information dissemination to its massive audience (Ezeonyejaku, Onyejelem & Nwokeocha, 2025).

Awareness about the dangers of drug abuse is the first step towards its prevention and intervention. Awareness and knowledge of these messages are crucial in shaping the attitudes and behaviours of young people towards drug use (Utalor, 2019; Egwu, 2022). Moreover, many young individuals lack comprehensive information about different drugs, their effects, and potential avenues for seeking help. The broadcast media serve as a valuable source of knowledge for the youth to be better informed about drugs, their usage, and the implications of drug abuse. The use of broadcast media in providing accurate and easily understandable information about drug abuse in different languages, using various formats and styles, can go a long way in creating a culture of drug free society.

Studies have shown that exposure to anti-drug messages through broadcast media can lead to increased awareness and knowledge about the dangers of drug abuse among youths (Egenti, Ebekue & Okafor, 2022; Adediran, 2023).

Studies have also demonstrated that broadcast media can reach a large audience, including hard-to-reach populations, and can be an effective medium for health communication (Utalor, 2019; Anwar, Malik, Raees & Anwar, 2020; Saei et al, 2021). By incorporating expert opinions, testimonials, and informative discussions, among other content, broadcast media messages can present a holistic view of drug abuse and equip the youths with the requisite knowledge for them to make informed decisions. Effective broadcast media messages can increase knowledge, shape attitudes, beliefs, and influence positive behaviour change among the youth concerning drug usage.

Consequences of Drug Abuse

The untoward effects on the individual drug user and the communities as a whole call for positive actions to reduce the incidence to its barest minimum. Drug abuse leaves its victims with increasing psychosocial, economic, health, and security challenges. Drug use disorders, according to Jianbo, Cong, Shunming, Lei & Jinghua (2023), are public health issues, with the attendant dependency or addiction challenge. Drug addiction in particular is not only a social issue but a health issue because drug use factors account for Global Burden of Disease GBD injuries and risk factor (Carter et al. 2015 in Jianbo, Cong, Shunming, Lei & Jinghua, 2023. Drug Use Disorders (DUD) accounted for 128.1 thousand deaths globally, which poses a challenge to the sustainable health system.

Broadcast media messages can play crucial roles in reducing this burden by highlighting the consequences of drug abuse on physical health, mental well-being, and overall quality of human life. Specifically, drug abuse can impact the users socially in the areas of employment or loss of jobs, expulsion from school or dropping out of school, stealing, armed robbery, rape, kidnapping, terrorism, and other criminal tendencies that can put the culprit in conflict with the law. It can also manifest in depletion of family income, family disintegration, and loss of life.

Furthermore, the physical health of victims of drug abuse could be negatively affected, leading to compromised health, such as liver problems, cancer, anemia, risk to the unborn child, hypertension, etc. On the psychological level, excessive drug use can lead to desire, dependency, and addiction, reduced coordination, sleeplessness or insomnia, panic attacks, and psychosis etc.

The power of visual and auditory messages conveyed through films, television, and radio has a profound impact on the viewer's perception and understanding of the issue. By employing persuasive techniques and relatable narratives,

broadcast media messages can effectively engage the youth and prompt them to rethink their choices regarding substance abuse.

Empirical Review

In Adekeye, Adeusi, Chenube, Ahaodu & Sholarin's (2015) study of "assessment of alcohol and substance use among undergraduates in selected private universities in Southwest Nigeria", the authors sampled 431 students aged between 15 and 25 from selected private tertiary institutions in Southwest Nigeria. The study used descriptive statistics in analyzing the collected data from an adapted and validated version of the World Health Organisation (2019) questionnaire and found that cigarette smoking accounted for the highest of the drugs abused by the students at 81%, closely followed by alcohol at 72%, and coffee, energy drinks, and kolanut followed at 69%. From the cited study, the gap that the present study fills could be seen as it is on Awka South LGA youths' level of awareness, knowledge, and use of broadcast media messages against drug abuse.

Moreover, in a cross-sectional study by Olarenwaju, Hamzat, Enya, Udekwu, Osuoya, Bamidele, Johnso, Johnson & Owolabi, (2022) on "an assessment of drug and substance abuse prevalence: A cross-sectional study among undergraduates in selected Southwestern universities in Nigeria," using a sample of 400 students including 100 male and female students in their 15-29 years of age, found a significant prevalence of drug and substance abuse across the selected universities in Southwest Nigeria. The current study is using a survey design to ascertain the level of awareness, knowledge, and use of broadcast messages against drug abuse among Awka South LGA youths in Anambra State, South-East Nigeria. A perusal of the topic and the areas of the two studies would show the gap that the present study stands to fill.

Also, Onyejelem, Ezeonyejiaku, Nwafor & Nwodu (2023) study on "portrayal of drug-related crimes among teenagers in Nollywood Movies: A critical discourse analysis on *Nimbe*", deployed critical discourse analysis (CDA) to analyze a Nigerian movie, *Nimbe* (2019). The study explored the problem of drug abuse among teenagers in Nigeria, and the findings reveal that the movie, *Nimbe*, did not expose the deep-rooted and remote causes of drug abuse among teens but simply tried to criminalize drug addiction. It also revealed that the movie portrayed the law enforcement agency as the principal tool to combat drug abuse and utterly disregarded the role of the media, particularly the broadcast media and other social institutions, such as educational, family, and health institutions that offer social support systems in curbing the menace of drug-related disorders. The position of the cited study shows the vacuum that the present

study, using the survey method, sought to close by assessing how the broadcast media messages can create awareness, to help the youths residing in Awka South LGA have knowledge of drug abuse.

Theoretical Framework

This study is guided by two theoretical frameworks: the Social Learning theory (SLT) and the Cognitive Dissonance Theory (CDT). The social learning theory propounded by Bandura (1977) argues that new behaviours can be learned by observation and imitation of others. It posits that learning occurs in a social context, and can be by observation of a behavioural trait or by direct instruction. The theory also believes that, by reward or punishment, behaviour is reinforced. This theory is relevant to this study because the desire to indulge in drug consumption, which could culminate in drug abuse, is a learned behaviour, which could be tamed through punishment or be encouraged through peer pressure or the satisfaction of personal desire to feel good by the users, known as vicarious reinforcement.

Cognitive dissonance theory, propounded by Festinger (1962), posits that there is a relationship between one's motivation, perceptions, and cognition. It tries to explain the conditions that motivate an individual to change his or her opinion, attitude, belief, or behaviour. Cooper (2007) states that people strive towards consistency within themselves and are motivated to adopt new behaviours either to reduce or eliminate inconsistency, that is, what does not align with their beliefs. The theory is of the view that cognitions are in pairs of relevant and irrelevant, which could be consistent with one's earlier beliefs; hence, the existence of dissonance would cause discomfort that would motivate the person to eliminate the discomforting cognition.

This theory is equally relevant in understanding the psychological processes that take place within a drug user, to either desist from consuming drugs, following messages that align with his/her beliefs, or simply reduce or eliminate such knowledge that is inconsistent with his/her perceptions.

By combining these two theories, this study aims to understand how awareness and knowledge of drug abuse risks, perceived benefits, and barriers influence youths' behaviour and decision-making related to drug use.

METHODOLOGY

The researchers adopted survey research method for this study because its primary data were gathered from the opinions of youths resident in Awka South Local Government Area, Anambra State; as Ohaja (2003, p.74) cited by Edogor,

Jonah and Ojo (2015, p.144) observe that where the views of any particular group or people forms the major source of primary data for a study, a survey would be called for. The population of the entire 9 communities in Awka South Local Government Area is projected as 270,300 according to City Population (2022). From the total population of the entire 9 communities in Awka South youths, a sample size of 357 was taken using Cozby's (2004) formula, considering the fact that the population of Awka South LGA youths is more than 5,000. The youths aged 18-35 years were randomly selected from 5 out of the 9 communities within the LGA. A haphazard sampling technique was used in getting the respondents, whereas a structured questionnaire was designed to elicit the data. The findings were analyzed and presented using tables and simple percentages.

Data presentation and analysis

Guided by the research objectives, research questions were raised to ascertain the respondents' opinions regarding the awareness, knowledge and uses of broadcast media messages against drug abuse. Only 7 out of the questionnaires distributed were found invalid for the study. Thus, 350 were usable.

The research objective No. 1 was to ascertain the level of awareness among youths in Awka South LGA about drug abuse and its use.

Source: Field work, 2024

The data presented in Figure 1 above revealed that a greater percentage (68%) of the respondents prefer to watch either films or television, while those who prefer radio are only 32%. This shows that the respondents are more likely to

access messages shared on movies and television about drug abuse, while a few others can access radio messages.

Table 1.2: Respondents' level of exposure to broadcast media

Source: Field work, 2024

The data presented in Figure 2 above revealed that (55.5%) respondents are exposed to the broadcast media messages, while (44.5%) of the respondents are hardly or rarely exposed to the messages. This implies that those who are actually exposed to the messages in the broadcast media are more than those who are not.

Source: Field work, 2024

The data presented in Figure 3 above revealed that (60.9%) of the respondents are exposed for more than 2-3 hours a day in the broadcast media, while (39.1%) respondents spend between one hour or less daily per day accessing the broadcast media content. This means that those who spend time on the broadcast media are more than those who do not.

Table 1: Respondents' preferred broadcast media programmes

Programmes	Frequency	Percentage
Talk shows	45	12.9
News & current affairs	43	12.3
Discussion	24	6.9
Commercials	35	10
Features	30	8.6
Interviews	26	7.4
Sports	55	15.7
Documentaries	36	10.2
Drama	44	12.6
Others	12	3.4
Total	350	100%

Source: Field work, 2024

The data presented in Table 1 above shows that sports programmes are the preferred programmes at 15.7%, followed by talk shows at 12.9%, and drama programmes came third with 12.6%. The least of the programmes in descending

order are documentaries at 10.2%, commercials at 10%, features at 8.6%, interviews at 7.4%, and discussion programmes at 6.9%, while others are only 3.4%. What this implies is that each format appeals to a particular set of respondents.

Table 2: Respondents’ knowledge of the broadcast media content messages on drug abuse

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
I learnt about the health hazards of drug abuse.	56	16
I heard about the social implications of drug abuse, such as crime and truancy among youths.	68	19.4
I heard that smokers are liable to die young.	127	36.3
I heard about the possible mental issues that can arise from drug use disorder.	52	14.9
I learnt that I might lose my job due to drug abuse.	47	13.4
Total	350	100%

Source: Field work, 2024.

The data presented in Table 3 above, which attempted to establish the specific cognitive items the respondents have learnt from the various broadcast contents, 16% learnt about the health implications of the messages, 19.4% picked the social implications as what they know, 36.3 heard that smokers, and may die young, 14.9% heard about the possible mental issues that can arise from drug usage, and 13.4% learnt about the economic losses they may have from drug abuse. This means that the respondents who were exposed to the various programmes in the broadcast media have learnt different things about the implications of drug abuse.

Table 3: Respondents’ uses of the drug abuse content message in the various broadcast media

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
I use the messages	64	18.3

sometimes.		
I stopped using drugs because of what I saw on TV.	42	12
The commercials instilled fear in me that made me rethink my drug habit.	36	10.3
I rarely adhered to the content messages.	89	25.4
I will continue using drugs because they help me to feel good.	45	12.9
I don't believe the pictures of addicts presented on TV as a reality.	74	21.1
Total	350	100%

Source: Field work, 2024.

The data presented in Table 4 above revealed that 18.3% of the respondents use the message content from the broadcast media; 12% stopped drug abuse following the content they were exposed to; 10.3 had a rethink because of the fear instilled on them by the commercials; 25.4 said they rarely adhered to the content messages; 21.1% said they do not believe the pictures of addicts on television as a reality. What these diverse responses imply is that while some have been influenced to change their behaviour, attitudes, and beliefs about drug abuse, some have simply dispelled the messages and continued their lifestyle of drug consumption, despite the broadcast media messages.

Table 4: Identifying the factors that influence the effectiveness of broadcast media messages in preventing drug abuse among youths of Awka South LGA.

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Meaningful message content	63	18
Frequency of message broadcast	76	21.7
Audience engagement	56	16
Choice of talents	66	18.9
Glamourisation of drugs	89	25.4

use in the broadcast media		
Total	350	100%

Source: field work, 2024

The data presented in Table 4 above revealed that 63 (18%) of the respondents are of the view that the way the contents are created was meaningful enough to influence their knowledge and use of broadcast media messages. Seventy-six (21.7%) point at the frequency of the broadcast as the factor that influenced them; 56 (16%) believe that the audience engagement style through phone-in programmes had much influence on them; 66 (18.9%) regard the choice of talents as their influencing factor; while 89 (25.4%) of the respondents view the mode of glamourisation of drug users in the broadcast media as a major source of influence for them. What these data imply is that the majority of the respondents (25.4% are of the view that glamourisation of drug users, especially in films and on television as rich and powerful individuals, makes them want to also be rich and powerful, hence the sense of belongingness can be achieved through drug use, regardless of the inherent dangers associated with drug abuse.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings revealed that the majority of the participants (80%) knew broadcast media messages on the risks associated with drug abuse from different programmes aired on radio and television, as well as messages through the films, which happens to be their most preferred medium (40%), followed closely by radio (32%), and television (28%). This shows that film is a more potent means of reaching young people in Nigeria, as corroborated by Onyejelem et al (2023). However, those who reportedly pay attention to the broadcast media messages on drug abuse were always 30.9% while 24.6% do so often. Sadly, those who hardly pay attention were 18.3% and 36.3% actually paying attention to these messages rarely. It means that the margin between those who pay attention to the messages was minimal compared to those who do not.

Furthermore, the study found a significant association between knowledge of broadcast media messages against drug abuse and the usage of these messages. Respondents who were aware and also had a high level of knowledge were more likely to utilize the messages. This notion aligns with Nwokedi et al. 2023's finding that people will respond to broadcast messages when the consequences are presented to them. Unlike those who hardly or rarely paid attention to the messages. Greater efforts should therefore be made to catch the youths using their preferred medium.

Additionally, respondents expressed a positive attitude and behaviour change towards the broadcast media messages in preventing drug abuse among youths. Although some respondents were still indifferent in using the knowledge, despite the messages found in the various broadcast media formats. This shows that though some persons may be aware and knowledgeable about an issue, yet, decide not to take the expected action, especially if such action is not consistent with their beliefs or interests. Findings from Table 5 of the study clearly show that a greater majority of the respondents, 25.4%, which is slightly more than a quarter of the respondents, say that media glamourisation of drug users influences their use of the broadcast media messages in changing their behaviour, hence the need to change the technique. This assertion agrees with Festinger (1962) and Cooper (2007) in their position on using cognitive dissonance to weigh two options.

CONCLUSION

This study analyzed the awareness, knowledge, and use of broadcast media messages against drug abuse in Awka South LGA. It also examined how these messages are currently utilized and what impact they have on the target audience. By assessing the existing broadcast media messages' reach, resonance, and effectiveness, the areas that require improvement should be determined to help address drug abuse among young people. The potency of broadcast media as powerful tools for combating drug abuse, through creating awareness and providing deep knowledge among the target audience, has been established as a way of increasing the fight against drug abuse among youths. Also, the high level of awareness and significant knowledge of broadcast media messages against drug abuse among youths in Awka-South LGA calls for the need to improve the use of the messages to fully combat drug abuse. The researchers suggest that further research should explore strategies to enhance the utilization of broadcast media for effective drug abuse prevention among youths.

Recommendations

From the results of this study, the researchers recommend the following:

1. Targeted educational campaign messages should be deployed to raise more awareness on the harmful effects of drug abuse among Nigerian youths.
2. Efforts should be made to counter the glamorisation of drug use in movies and television dramas.
3. The negative effects of drug abuse should be aired in different languages to reach a wider audience in their local languages.

4. In this age of social media, targeted campaign messages on the negative consequences of drug abuse should also be placed on various online platforms to reach the youths who are increasingly found online.
5. Further studies should be conducted to explore strategies to enhance the utilization of broadcast media for effective drug abuse prevention among youths.

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Author's Contributions

Njideka Ezeonyjiaku conceived the idea of this paper and wrote the first draft with Dr Obiorah Edogor; Njideka also coordinated the data gathering with Timothy Onyejelem; Nneoma Okoye did the proofreading, and Chisom Ubaezuonu reworked the paper based on the comments from the reviewers.

Declaration of Conflict of Interest

We, the authors hereby declare that there was no conflict of interest with any sources or persons from the beginning of this paper to the end of it.

Ethical clearance

The authors kindly sought and duly obtained the necessary ethical clearance from each of the respondents who provided the data used for this paper. We pledged confidentiality and anonymity of the personal details and views of each respondents and we kept to our promise to all of them.

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REFERENCES

Adediran, I.A. (2023). An assessment of the broadcast media campaigns against drug abuse in Nigeria. *International Journal of International Relations, media and mass Communication Studies*. 9(2), pp.42-56. <https://www.eajournals.org/>.

- Adekeye, O.A., Adeusi, S.O., Chenube, O.O., Ahaodu, F.O. & Sholarin, M.A. (2015). Assessment of alcohol and substance use among undergraduates in selected private universities in Southwest Nigeria. *Journal of Humanities and Social Science, IOSR, JHSS* 20(3), 1-7. <https://www.scrip.org/reference/referencespapers?referenceid=3487812>
- Adeyeye, C.M. (2018). Abuse of psychoactive drugs in Nigeria: Our problem. Speech by Prof. Christianah Mojisola Adeyeye, Director General, NAFDAC, at the flag-off of drug abuse awareness campaign in Kano. <https://nafdac.gov.ng/abuse-of-psychoactive-drugs-in-nigeria-our-problem-by-prof-christianah-mojisola-adeyeye/>
- Bandura, A. (1977). *Social Learning Theory*. Oxford, England: Prentice-Hall.
- City population (2022). Anambra (State, Nigeria)- population Statistics, charts, maps and location. https://www.citypopulation.de/en.nigeria/admin/NGA004_anambra/
- Cooper, J. (2007). *Cognitive dissonance*. London: Sage Publications Limited.
- Cozby, P. (2004). *Methods in behavioural research*. Boston: McGraw-Hill.
- Edogor, O. I., Ambassador-Brikins, H.O.C. & Ezika, C. G. (2020). Non-Usage of Indigenous Language for Political Mobilisation on Radio: Implications on Igala-Speaking Voters of South-East, Nigeria During the 2019 Elections. *BABCOCK Journal of Mass Communication*, 16-34.
- Edogor, O.I., Jonah, A. A., & Ojo, L. I. (2015). Nigerian Users' Evaluation of Credibility of Social Media Sites. *New Media and Mass Communication*, 40, 139-150, <http://www.iiste.org/Journals/index.php/NMMC/article/download/24941/25544>.
- Egenti, M.C., Ebekue, E.O. & Okafor, K.A. (2022). An evaluation of the effectiveness of communication channels and campaign messages employed in the fight against COVID-19 in Anambra State. *Creative Artists: A Journal of Theatre and Media Studies*. 16(2). https://ajol-file-journals_456_articles_253123_64df22f68e4e5.pdf.
- Egwu, E.O. (2022). Broadcast media contents in shaping audience attitude towards environmental sanitation in Nigeria. *Path of Science International Electronic Scientific Journal*. 8(12), <https://pathofscience.org/index.php/ps/article/view/1474>.

- Elom, C.O., Uwakwe, R.C., Akpa, S.I. & Uwaleke, C.C. (2025). Impact of drug abuse on mental health of secondary school students in Abakaliki, Ebonyi State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Scientific Studies*, 8(3), 4362-4369. <https://doi.org/10.53894/ijirss.v8i3.7511>.
- Ezeonyejaku, N.P., Onyejelem, T.E., & Nwokeocha, M. I. (2025). Breast cancer knowledge, attitude, and practice of OCI CerviBreast App campaign message on ABS 88.5 FM Radio, Awka, among undergraduate students of Nnamdi Azikiwe University. *IJREAL: International Journal of Religion, Education and Law* 4(2), 130-144.
- Festinger, L. (1962). *A theory of cognitive dissonance*. Stanford: Stanford University Press.
- Jatau, A.I., Sha'aban, A., Gulma, K.A., Shitu, Z., Khalid, G.M., Isa, A., Wada, A.S., & Mustapha, M. (2021). The burden of drug abuse in Nigeria: A scoping review of epidemiological studies and drug laws. <https://www.sspjournal.org/journals/public-health-reviews/articles/10.3389/phrs.2021.1603960/full>.
- Jianbo, S., Guangyao, H., Cong, L., Shunming, L, Lei, L., & Jinhua, J. (2023). Prevalence, incidence, deaths, and disability-adjusted life-years of drug use disorders for 204 countries and territories during the past 30 years. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S1876201823002332>.
- Lynch, S.S. (2022). Overview of drugs. MSD Manual consumer version. <https://www.msdmanuals.com/home/drugs/overview-of-drugs/overview-of-drugs>.
- Mazhari, S., Ziaddini, H., Nakhaee, N. & Kermanian, A. (2021). Drug abuse prevalence among 10th-12th-grade students of Kerman, Iran in 2017-2018 academic year. *Journal of Advanced Immunopharmacology*, 1(3). <https://doi.org/10.5812/tms.115848>.
- Nabofa, O. O. (2021). New trend of drug abuse by secondary school students in Nigeria. 21(3): 1460-1466. <https://doi.org/10.4314/ahs.v21i3.57>.
- Nahvizadeh, M.M., Akhara, S., Arti, S., Qaraat, L., Geramian, N., & Farjzadegan, Z. (2014). A review study on substance abuse status in High School Students, Isfahan, Iran. *International Journal of Preventive Medicine*, 5(2); S77-S82. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/pmc4476010/>

- National Cancer Institute, NCI Dictionary of Cancer Terms (n.d.). What are drugs? Retrieved from: <https://www.cancer.gov/publications/dictionaries/cancer-terms/def/drug>.
- Nnamani, F.U. (2017). A comparative assessment of broadcast media and social media as tools for national development in Nigeria. *IMT International Journal of the Arts and Sciences*. 3(5), 63-75.
- Nwokedi, O.P., Akata, U. & Mba, J.U. (2023). Effectiveness of broadcast messages as a panacea to drug abuse in South-East Nigeria. *University of Nigeria Interdisciplinary Journal of Communication Studies*. No. 29, pp. 120-130.
- Olarenwaju, J.A., Hamzat, E.O., Enya, J.I., Udekwu, M.O., Osuoya, Q., Bamidele, R., Johnson, O.F., Johnson, B.S., & Owolabi, J.O. (2022). An assessment of drug and substance abuse prevalence: A cross-sectional study among undergraduates in selected Southwestern universities in Nigeria. *Journal of International Medical Research*, 25; 50(10). <https://doi.org/10.1177/03000605221130039>.
- Onyejelem, T.E., Ezeonyejiaku, N. P., Nwafor, O. A, & Nwodu, G. E. (2023). Portrayal of drug-related crimes among teenagers in Nollywood movies: A critical discourse analyses". *IMSU Journal of Communication Studies*. 7(2), 156-168. <https://nbn-resolving.org/urn:de:0168-SSoar-91294-5>.
- Saei, M.H, Valadi, S., Karimi, K. & Khammarnia, M. (2021). The role of mass media communication in public health: The impact of Islamic Republic of Iran broadcasting health channel on health literacy and health behaviour. *Medical Journal of the Islamic Republic of Iran*. <https://doi.org/10.47176/mjiri.35.54>.
- Sloboda, Z. (2020). Drug abuse epidemiology: An overview. *Bulletin on Narcotics*. 2002 Liv (1&2). https://www.researchgate.net/publication/287633884_Drug+abuse+epidemiology+An+overview/references.
- United Nations Office on Drug and Crimes, UNODC (2023). World Drug Report. (EN/AR/Ru?ZH) -World <https://reliefweb.int/report/worldunodc-world-drug-report-2023>.
- Utalor, U.J. (2019). Influence of broadcast media messages, perception and attitude of maternal health among reproductive women in Ilorin. *Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Research*. 2(1), 57-116. <https://abjournals.org/african-journal-of-social-sciences-and-humanities-research->

[ajsshr/wp-content/uploads/sites/9/journal/published__paper/volume-2/issue-1 /AJSSHR_UQIbftw8.pdf](https://ajsshr/wp-content/uploads/sites/9/journal/published__paper/volume-2/issue-1/AJSSHR_UQIbftw8.pdf).

Vanguard (July 29, 2023). 14.3m Nigerians involved in drug abuse – NDLEA. Retrieved from: <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2023/07/14-3-million-nigerians-involved-in-drug-abuse-ndlea/>.

World Health Organization (2019). Management of substance abuse facts and figures. <https://www.who.int/substanceabuse/facts/en/>.